

- Responding to the need for an Operations Research/Data Analytics standard, philosophically
- In support of AIM's "Free the US" project (www.FREETH.us); the anti-ESG economic score

MESS 0007

MIMS 2.101: The ORDA Standard

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ABSTRACT

Operations Research and Data Analytics need a philosophical guide to the scientific endeavors (in the author's opinion). This short MESSy puts forth a proposed standard as well as a plea to the ORDA community to review, adopt, and develop this standard, while protecting it from the worst POS and Lying Liars that currently use Big Data for "evil." Ironic, since it was the founders of Google who set out the brand, "Don't be Evil." But, nevertheless, we are where we are, and the 2022 slogan is: "It is what It Is." Still, we can do better, and the ORDAINED standard will "set the record straight," as to what a Tough-Minded Managed business will utilize in a post-COVID/post-2020 world.

Keywords: Operations Research - Data - Analytics - Business - Standards - Computation

Operations Research + Data Analytics

Operations Research¹ (OR) is a science invented in the second World War by the Americans, and may be partially attributed to the many reasons why the USA was the unstoppable dark horse that won it all for the Allies. Data Analytics² (DA) was born out of OR combined with computation. Computation was identified in the SPACERS³ work, “Conquering the Solar System,”⁴ by the author as one of the three keys⁵ to accelerate success in that endeavor. Nevertheless, not every corporation is spending UPS level money - even still - on ORDA, and it has become a bit gouache to have the funding; but it is **absolutely vital** in the World War 3.0⁶ (and web 3.0) era to have a data analytical team, head, or department. In fact, this author feels that the next step is the provision of a true ORDA standard - philosophically - which is “plug n play” with the dual layer economics and with “business circuitry.”

MIMS 2.101 The ORDAINED (or ORDA) Standard

Figure 1 - The ORDAINED framework is a standard any AIMster or PEMster could get behind; credit: author

The purpose of Operations is to produce results. The purpose of Research, as a MIMS, is to find future ideas and their scientific utility (MIMS 1.0+2.0)^{7,8}. The purpose of Data is to have evidence, and utilize the N power. The purpose of Analytics is to solve data sets that reveal reality.

In order to have these things work together, we need the **right kind of paired standards**, with - as shown - cross threading (an AIM ‘quadrant’ in AIM 2.0)⁹.

¹ <https://www.britannica.com/topic/operations-research>

² <https://www.techtarget.com/searchdatamanagement/definition/data-analytics>

³ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc/spacers>

⁴ https://www.academia.edu/62757621/Conquering_the_Solar_System

⁵ The other two being True Green Energy (including deep mining), and Pre-engineering/Presearch (mostly involving AI).

⁶ <https://www.amazon.com/dp/1643384368/ref=olp-opf-redir?od=1>

⁷

https://www.academia.edu/50300514/On_the_Membranous_Interface_of_the_Material_and_the_Spiritual_from_an_EPEMC_perspective_and_Dual_Double_Layer_Economics_a_proposed_test_of_EPEMCs_metallic_properties_tensile_strength_malleability_durability

⁸ https://www.academia.edu/50804855/MIMS_2_Applications_discussions

⁹ <https://bit.ly/3qGdVx9>

- ❖ Implementation here is a double standard, in that it also refers back to a Resilient Way¹⁰ standard known as OOPSIE. Nevertheless, it is a general *Rockefeller Habit*¹¹ in business, and for that matter the strength inherently implied in a *Midas Touch*¹² (standard), to achieve **traction**. Traction implies that things are [efficiently] implemented.
- ❖ Numericalization is an effort to move mathematics back towards a form of predictive analytics which are hopefully less formulaic and more data-based.
 - “Give me Data or Give me Death”
- ❖ Efficiency is, of course, about achieving more power (or profundity) in lessening time, since power is Work over Time.
 - Efficacy is [currently] at a G⁴ standard:
 - Getting it done
 - Getting it done *right*
 - “Getting out while the getting is good” (still)
 - Efficacy implies the potency we desire behind our potency, and power.
- ❖ Definition is a matter of resolution
 - Refinement of Vision or Image
 - Determination
 - Dependability on these definitions and in communicated (discourse) data packets (daether)
 - D⁵ resolution standard

IN - Relying on Data

The issue with statistics is all the lies, damned-lies, and God-damned lies that come with it. Mostly people lie to themselves, but they also lie to each other (We Work, anyone?) Therefore, since “that dog don’t hunt,” when it comes to fakery and fraud we must rely on the verification process. “Trust, but verify,” is an old Russian proverb¹³ made famous by President Reagan. However, verification itself has become suspect. “How can we rely on Data?” is also a pertinent question after everything that has happened since 2020 (rigged elections, COVID lies, Big Pharma, Russia invasion, Tech censorship, etc.) This problem itself probably won’t go away soon, either. Therefore the verification process is not a mere matter of encryption, or energy usage - both E’s in the SPACERS standard - but it is a matter of **fact-based empirical study**. As much as possible, we eliminate the BS and sophistry of political discourse and politicization of business, especially anything related to Political Correctness, and *drill down with Tough-Mindedness* to the bedrock. That bedrock might be the “bottom line” or “how many widgets we can make” (KPI), or it might be the hard facts of customer feedback and market viability, sentiment, and vulnerability to volatility. It needs, however, to be measured, defined, and above all honest, which we will here define as both genuine (the ‘genuine article’) and trustworthy. If it is not honest data (think: Twitter’s numbers provided to Elon Musk on bots vs. number of users), then there is not only no reason to trust the data, there is no reason to trust the source, company, outlet, report, etc. In these rare cases, we might “throw the baby out with the bathwater.” To the lying liars¹⁴ caught lying still, we will say “you’re Fired!”

¹⁰ www.resilient-way.com

¹¹ <https://bit.ly/37UEAxT>

¹² <https://bit.ly/3Cj3Z44>

¹³ Dovyrai, no provyrai (Доверяй, но проверяй) https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Trust,_but_verify

¹⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lies_and_the_Lying_Liars_Who_Tell_Them This man was unfairly #metoo’d and was one of the last good Democrats ever. The party flipped on him, because he was never a Lying Liar (insider POS Supreme).

ED - Create a clear picture of the Work Order

Work is sacred, and time, energy, money, and manpower are related to quintessence (Jing 京), and health. People should not be abused, no matter if it is capitalist or any other economic system. They should be recompensed, and well, for their data and energy loss through efforts applied. If they are extremely efficient and/or efficacious, and they provide potency, they should be **handsomely rewarded** and cozened. Why? They've clearly put in the work to become potent. Therefore, we recommend the Numericalization of what is IN be both well-defined and efficient communication and above all: dependable. If it is dependable, then the trustworthiness issue with verification above will be clear.

Proposal

The author proposes a movement *and analytical school or method* be invented/pre-engineered and eventually engineered which *mimsically advances* ORDA to the ORDAINED standard. Let the future of Data - the power of Numbers distilled down to pure numerical Value-Fields in the living moment of the passing PPPC 'window' or 'image', be considered sacrosanct. Let it be literally *ordained by God*, and the *G, A, and L* powers¹⁵ flow downward into the vessel of mimsical design (probably software, but not only.) When this flow is completed, and the data matrix compiled, let it be verified, certified, compressed, stretched, and *enriched* - even translated into 2D, 3D, or higher dimensions... or perhaps down to 1D if it was a larger data set - so that it can be utilized in computational scale according to the AIM standard¹⁶:

- **Aim** for scalability is Advancement
- **Implement** repeatability is the Idea
- **Maintain** scriptability is the Mechanics

Conclusion

The author would like to see the ORDAINED standard applied to the FREETH score, to produce an algorithm that can reliably eliminate the evil ESG score which is put forward by the POS's in order to destroy the Allies, primarily America. If it is maintained through the AI (r)evolution to the Quantum Supremacy age, it may just as of yet save humanity from death by 10,000 ignorant cuts. Right now, the sea of Data is not only too large, but it is fraught with actual, factual dangers. These dangers are not unrelated to the evils (anti-MIMS) which beset mankind... not the least of which is the ease and unpunishability of lies. Statistical lies can be dealt with, but the System no longer holds to account those that have no standards. This process might begin to undo this issue. Then again, it might only add gasoline to the fire. A dæthereal analysis would render (with some resolution) the truth of this.

Oh and the ORDAINED standard cannot/must not be under the sway or control of the Secret Societies, Deep State, Corporatocracy, or other POS¹⁷ (Peer Review Cult¹⁸, politicians, etc.). It must remain a MIMS, and never be allowed to become an anti-MIMS. **Too much leverage is at stake.**

¹⁵ Lord→Force→Aether (Heaven)→Numbers (where the math tool comes from, etc.)→Physics→GOD /\ https://www.academia.edu/53271235/Explication_of_the_Versatility_of_the_Big_G_diagram_in_MIMS_1_0

¹⁶ <https://bit.ly/3oezRhD>

¹⁷ https://www.academia.edu/87490521/MESS0006_The_POS_Wave_continues_because_Agenda

¹⁸ https://www.academia.edu/74466574/The_Peer_Review_Cult_cover_up_Conspiracy_Facts_the_fact_checkers_do_not_want_you_to_know_about

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